

FishFORWRD

FishFORWRD v2.2.1 Update

May 2026

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FishFORWRD Update: May 2026

This update integrates project submissions from FishFORWRD forms, updates from [Offshore Research Funder Coordination](#) sessions, and other ROSA coordination efforts, alongside community-provided corrections.

Project Additions and Gaps Analysis Mapping

A total of 36 research and monitoring efforts have been added in this update, with comprehensive data accessible via the FishFORWRD platform.

Following the March 2026 release of the [Fish and Fisheries Offshore Wind Research Gaps Analysis final report](#), all projects are now mapped to a framework of 70 Summarized Research Needs (SRNs). These SRNs, established through a rigorous peer review, facilitate an ongoing evaluation of which critical scientific questions are being actively investigated and which remain unaddressed. Access [the complete list of SRNs here](#).

Please note that SouthCoast Wind fisheries monitoring surveys have been removed as part of this update pending verification of their official implementation dates.

The table below is a summary of new projects and the research need(s) they address. Full project information is available within FishFORWRD.

Project ID	Research Category	Project Title	Lead Entity	Funder	Summarized Research Need(s) Addressed
Ex-247	Socioeconomic & Sociocultural Impact	Value-added analysis for first-sale seafood businesses in the U.S. Mid-Atlantic and Northeast	Virginia Institute of Marine Science	Scemfis	SRN-55: Secondary and Tertiary Effects to Supply Chains and Supporting Businesses
Ex-248	Cumulative Impacts & Fisheries Management Implications	Feasibility of Offshore Wind Farm Areas as Multi-Use Platforms for Lower-Trophic Aquaculture	Virginia Institute of Marine Science	ASMFC	SRN-56: Marine Spatial Planning and Use Tradeoffs
Ex-249	Regional Resource Monitoring	Regional Surfclam Monitoring Plan	NYS Fisheries Technical Working Group (Tetra Tech)	NYSERDA	SRN-10: Design and Evaluate Strategies for Regional Scale Monitoring

Project ID	Research Category	Project Title	Lead Entity	Funder	Summarized Research Need(s) Addressed
Ex-250	Sound/Vibration Impacts	Offshore windfarm construction elevates metabolic rate and increases predation vulnerability of a key marine invertebrate	Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution	BOEM Environmental Studies Program	SRN-41: Effects of Offshore Wind Sound on Behavior and Physiology of Fish and Shellfish
Ex-251	Cumulative Impacts & Fisheries Management Implications	Flyway Models and Metrics in the Assessment of OWF Impacts on Migratory Fishes	University of Maryland Center for Environmental Science	ROSA	SRN-1: Cumulative Impact Assessment Framework/Guidance; SRN-14: Use of Historical Datasets to Generate Baselines; SRN-17: Effects of Offshore Wind Development Phases on Spatial Behavior
Ex-252	Data Management	Development of Interactive Data Layers for Visualization of Fisheries Monitoring Surveys	INSPIRE Environmental Venterra Group	ROSA	SRN-9: Data Integration and Tool Building
Ex-253	Fishing Access	Co-Locating a Fixed Fishing Gear with a Demonstration Scale Floating Offshore Wind Turbine: Quantifying gear loss and developing fixed gear fishing strategies around the VoltturnUS+ demonstration scale wind turbine	University of Maine	ROSA	SRN-50: Spatial Operation Needs Within and Around Wind Farms
Ex-254	Regional Resource Monitoring	Increasing the utility of acoustic telemetry data to inform decision making and assessments at the project and regional scale	Smithsonian Environmental Research Center	ROSA	SRN-12: Regional Acoustic Receiver Array
Ex-255	Survey Adaptation	Data Integration and Evaluation of Autonomous, Multi-frequency	ASA Analysis & Communication, Inc.	ROSA	SRN-66: Alternate and Advanced Technologies and Survey Techniques

		Acoustic Surveys for Monitoring Regional Pelagic Ecosystems at Offshore Wind Leases			
Project ID	Research Category	Project Title	Lead Entity	Funder	Summarized Research Need(s) Addressed
Ex-256	Habitat Fragmentation/Modification	Spatiotemporal & Habitat Suitability Modeling for Sea Scallops in the Mid-Atlantic Bight	Stony Brook University	NYSERDA	SRN-31: Baseline Benthic and Water Column Habitat
Ex-257	Fishing Access	Fishermen Led Gear Innovation in Southern New England	FV Martha Elizabeth	Massachusetts Fisheries Innovation Fund	SRN-51: Gear Modification, Fisheries Enhancement, and Other Fisheries Development to Allow Co-Use
Ex-258	Fishing Access	Novel fish potting with lights for black seabass and scup: Developing innovative fishing gear for safe and efficient operation in offshore wind farm areas	University of Massachusetts Dartmouth SMAST	Massachusetts Fisheries Innovation Fund	SRN-51: Gear Modification, Fisheries Enhancement, and Other Fisheries Development to Allow Co-Use
Ex-259	Fishing Access	Evaluating the Hazard of Trawling Over Cable Protection Mattresses	Commercial Fisheries Research Foundation	Massachusetts Fisheries Innovation Fund	SRN-52: Fishing Interaction with Cable Protection Measures; SRN-54: Navigation and Safety
Ex-260	Fishing Access	Advancing Mechanical Jigging to Strengthen Squid Fishery Resilience Amid Offshore Wind Development	Commercial Fisheries Research Foundation	Massachusetts Fisheries Innovation Fund	SRN-51: Gear Modification, Fisheries Enhancement, and Other Fisheries Development to Allow Co-Use
Ex-261	Socioeconomic & Sociocultural Impact	Measuring Impacts of Offshore Wind on Commercial Fishing Fleets in Southern New England	University of Rhode Island	Northeast Sea Grant Consortium	Spatial and Temporal Change in Commercial and Recreational Fishing Behavior;

					Marine Spatial Planning and Use Tradeoffs
Project ID	Research Category	Project Title	Lead Entity	Funder	Summarized Research Need(s) Addressed
Ex-262	Habitat Fragmentation/Modification	Assessing the Recruitment Dynamics and Impacts of Offshore Wind Development on Larval Atlantic Sea Scallops with a Novel 47-Year Dataset along the U.S. Northeast Shelf	Coonamesett Farm Foundation	NOAA RSA Program	SRN-14: Use of Historical Datasets to Generate Baselines; SRN-23: Larval Transport and Recruitment Effects
Ex-263	EMF	Offshore Electric and Magnetic Field Assessment Beacon Wind Project	Integral Consulting Inc.	BP	SRN-39: Ecological Risk Assessment Approaches, Methods and Models
Ex-264	Fisheries Engagement & Capacity Building	FINsight: Fishing Industry Insights	ROSA	ROSA	SRN-47: Local Ecological Knowledge Methodology Development and Integration
Ex-265	Fishing Access	The Role of Economics in Offshore Wind Development Using Commercial Fishery Economics to Evaluate Offshore Wind Impacts	Veritas Economics	Undetermined	SRN-60: Methods for Evaluating Socioeconomic/Sociocultural Impact
Ex-266	Regional Resource Monitoring	Tale of two tags: Using satellite telemetry to evaluate the relative effectiveness of regional acoustic telemetry for monitoring large animal presence in relation to offshore wind activity	New England Aquarium	New Jersey RMI	SRN-12: Regional Acoustic Receiver Array
Ex-267	Habitat Fragmentation/Modification	Optimizing Benthic Monitoring to Evaluate Regional Effects of Offshore Wind Development	INSPIRE Environmental Venterra Group	New Jersey RMI	SRN-28: Effect of Artificial Substrate on Benthic and Epibenthic

		on Benthic Function within the NJ-NY Bight Region			Community; SRN-31: Baseline Benthic and Water Column Habitat; SRN-34: Change in Water and Sediment Quality
Project ID	Research Category	Project Title	Lead Entity	Funder	Summarized Research Need(s) Addressed
Ex-268	Data Management	Regional Offshore Wind Fisheries Data Governance for the New York-New Jersey Bight	ROSA	New Jersey RMI	SRN-1: Cumulative Impact Assessment Framework/Guidance; SRN-8: Enhance Data Governance
Ex-269	Socioeconomic & Sociocultural Impact	The seafood economy in the face of change: Socioeconomic analyses to support industry adaptation to offshore wind	Virginia Institute of Marine Science	New Jersey RMI	SRN-55: Secondary and Tertiary Effects to Supply Chains and Supporting Businesses; SRN-57: Approaches to, Data Inputs for, and Assessment of Compensatory Mitigation Programs
Ex-270	Cumulative Impacts & Fisheries Management Implications	Offshore wind and aquaculture co-location: challenges and opportunities in US Federal Waters	NOAA NCCOS	NOAA National Ocean Service	SRN-56: Marine Spatial Planning and Use Tradeoffs
Ex-271	Species Distribution/Composition	Spatiotemporal Distributions of Species Detected within Virginia's Offshore Lease Areas	Chesapeake Bay LLC	BOEM Environmental Studies Program	SRN-17: Effects of Offshore Wind Development Phases on Spatial Behavior
Ex-272	Fishing Access	Boulder Relocation for Offshore Energy Development in Rhode Island: Artificial Reefs and Cross-Industry Collaboration	Marine Affairs Institute at Roger Williams University School of Law and the Rhode Island Sea Grant Legal Program	Undetermined	SRN-53: Impacts of Boulder Relocation on Fishing

Project ID	Research Category	Project Title	Lead Entity	Funder	Summarized Research Need(s) Addressed
Ex-273	Data Management	VW 1 Gear Innovation Fund, Massachusetts Lobstermen's Association and Deckhand	The Massachusetts Lobstermen's Association	Vineyard Wind	SRN-6: Enhance Application of Fishery Dependent Data; SRN-47: Local Ecological Knowledge Methodology Development and Integration
Ex-274	Species Distribution/Com position	Forecasting Species Distribution Shifts in a Warming Gulf of Maine: Implications for Fisheries and Offshore Wind Development	University of New England	Maine Community Foundation	SRN-15: Changes to Biological Indicators of Incidence, Local Abundance and Distribution, Habitat Suitability, and Community Structure
Ex-275	Fishing Access	Development of a fully coupled, non-hydrostatic, marine infrastructure-resolving atmosphere and ocean model system in the U.S. Northeast	University of Massachusetts Dartmouth SMAST	U.S. Coast Guard	SRN-22: Local and Regional Changes to Ocean Hydrodynamics; SRN-54: Navigation and Safety
Ex-276	Habitat Fragmentation/ Modification	Deployment of bottom-mounted echosounders and ADCPs to assess potential physical and biological impacts of offshore wind developments	NOAA NEFSC	NOAA NEFSC	SRN-22: Local and Regional Changes to Ocean Hydrodynamics
Ex-277	Fishing Access	Legal Limits on Recreational Fishing Near Offshore Wind Facilities	Marine Affairs Institute at Roger Williams University School of Law and the Rhode Island Sea Grant Legal Program	Undetermined	SRN-49: Spatial and Temporal Change in Commercial and Recreational Fishing Behavior
Ex-278	Socioeconomic & Sociocultural Impact	Coastal Zone Management Act Consistency Review and Fisheries	Marine Affairs Institute at Roger Williams University School of Law	NOAA Sea Grant	SRN-57: Approaches to, Data Inputs for, and Assessment of Compensatory Mitigation Programs

		Compensation Mitigation	and the Rhode Island Sea Grant Legal Program		
Project ID	Research Category	Project Title	Lead Entity	Funder	Summarized Research Need(s) Addressed
Ex-279	Socioeconomic & Sociocultural Impact	Vessel Liability for Allisions and Gear Entanglements with Offshore Wind Turbines	Marine Affairs Institute at Roger Williams University School of Law and the Rhode Island Sea Grant Legal Program	NOAA Sea Grant	SRN-54: Navigation and Safety
Ex-280	Socioeconomic & Sociocultural Impact	Fisheries Compensation Agreements & Offshore Wind - Connecticut	Marine Affairs Institute at Roger Williams University School of Law and the Rhode Island Sea Grant Legal Program	NOAA Sea Grant	SRN-57: Approaches to, Data Inputs for, and Assessment of Compensatory Mitigation Programs
Ex-281	Socioeconomic & Sociocultural Impact	Fisheries Compensation Agreements & Offshore Wind - New York	Marine Affairs Institute at Roger Williams University School of Law and the Rhode Island Sea Grant Legal Program	NOAA Sea Grant	SRN-57: Approaches to, Data Inputs for, and Assessment of Compensatory Mitigation Programs
Ex-282	Species Distribution/Com position	Baseline Dynamics of Black sea bass in an offshore wind farm area	University of Massachusetts Dartmouth SMAST	Vineyard Wind	Changes to Growth, Feeding, Reproduction, Recruitment, and Mortality; Artificial Reef Effect on Fish; Effects on Spawning Timing, Location, and Habitat Use

ROSA encourages submission of any missing or newly launched offshore fisheries research projects through the following link: <https://forms.office.com/r/KK5wu41Z6u>

Corrections and updates to existing projects can be submitted through the following link: <https://forms.office.com/r/JfNNMKfmA4>

New Research Needs

No new research needs in this update.

Updates to the Webtool

No updates to the webtool were made.

Next Steps

As new research and monitoring projects come online, ROSA will continue to add projects to FishFORWRD and assign them to the relevant research needs to maintain an updated project database and associated Research Gaps Analysis.

ROSA has also announced a webinar series: ***The State of Offshore Wind Fisheries Science on the U.S. Atlantic Coast***

The Research Gaps Analysis identifies where research exists and what research needs are being addressed, but it does not capture what that research has found to date. With over half of the projects in FishFORWRD scheduled to be completed by the end of 2025, research and monitoring results are beginning to accumulate. ROSA is excited to launch a webinar series designed to bridge that gap by synthesizing and sharing findings from completed and mature projects mapped to research needs important to the ROSA Community. Keep updated by subscribing to our newsletter:

rosascience.org/newsletter-signup

Background

The Responsible Offshore Science Alliance (ROSA) in conjunction with WSP USA, Inc. (WSP) has developed the ROSA Fish and Fisheries OffshoRe Wind Research Database (FishFORWRD) to provide a platform for interested stakeholders to view and learn of new and existing funded research projects and stated research needs in the offshore wind fisheries space on the U.S. east coast. FishFORWRD catalogs all research, monitoring efforts, and stated research needs for offshore wind, fish, and fisheries. This database differentiates ongoing projects funded to examine offshore wind interactions from other programs that provide valuable data, but which haven't necessarily been designed to assess offshore wind impacts. The objective of FishFORWRD is to increase awareness of ongoing work, avoid duplication of efforts, and create a common understanding of research needs. This tool is meant for research funders, fisheries and offshore wind researchers, offshore wind developers, and the public.

FishFORWRD was first released on ROSA's website in 2022 as an excel sheet complete with tables of ongoing research and research needs, as well as a pivot table to provide a gaps analysis of which research needs were currently being addressed by funded projects and which research needs still remained. The associated [report](#) outlines how to use this first version of the databases and how the database was created. In an effort to make this information more accessible, ROSA and WSP have continued their partnership to 1. update the database with new research projects and research needs announced since 2022; 2. create an interactive webtool to view, filter, and download information held within FishFORWRD.

Through mining of relevant sources, effective communication with the inaugural ROSA Offshore Wind Fisheries Funder Coordination Meeting held in May 2024, and one-on-one meetings held with each offshore wind developer, FishFORWRD v2.1.0 was released featuring an updated list of funded research projects, each fisheries monitoring survey being conducted for each developers implemented Fisheries Monitoring Plan, and each relevant research need from 17 different published documents by federal agencies, states agencies, and public-private partnerships. Research projects are included within FishFORWRD if they are conducted within the U.S. East Coast and funded to investigate effects of offshore wind on fish and fisheries. FishFORWRD v2.1.0 shared this information on an interactive webtool that allows for filtering projects and research needs by location,

receptor, methodology, funder, and more. Lastly, the webtool provides submission forms for new projects, new research needs, and any requested corrections.

In March 2026, ROSA finalized the Fish and Fisheries Offshore Wind Research Gaps Analysis and released a [final report](#). Through a structured peer review process, a set of 70 summarized research needs (SRNs) were identified that structure the offshore wind fisheries research landscape. Each research and monitoring project in FishFORWRD was evaluated and mapped to one or more SRNs they address, enabling an assessment of whether each of the 70 summarized research needs are currently being explored by one or more projects or remain unaddressed. [The full set of summarized research needs can be found here](#).

As new research and monitoring projects come online, ROSA will continue to add projects to FishFORWRD and assign them to the relevant research needs to maintain an updated Gaps Analysis.

Previous Updates

Responsible Offshore Science Alliance (ROSA). (2024). Fish and Fisheries OffshoRe Wind Research Database (FishFORWRD) (2.1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17407181>.

Responsible Offshore Science Alliance (ROSA). (2025). Fish and Fisheries OffshoRe Wind Research Database (FishFORWRD) (2.1.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17407483>.

Responsible Offshore Science Alliance (ROSA). (2025). Fish and Fisheries OffshoRe Wind Research Database (FishFORWRD) (2.2.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17442098>.